

Effect of Solvent Interaction on the Absorption Spectra of Anhydro Salts derived from 1-Azacarbazole, 2-Azacarbazole and their 6-Nitro Derivatives

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The absorption spectra of anhydro salts derived from 1-azacarbazole, 2-azacarbazole and their 6-nitro derivatives show a characteristic absorption maximum in the longer wavelength which is not present in the parent base. The betaine formulation for anhydro salts satisfies the requirements for this characteristic absorption. The absorption spectra of these anhydro salts show considerable dependence on the type of solvent used. There is a bathochromic shift in the absorption maxima in solvents of decreasing dipole moment and they suffer a hypsochromic shift in hydroxylic solvent. The former effect is attributed to the alignment of the polar solvent molecules with those of the anhydro salt and the latter, to the hydrogen bonding with anionic nitrogen. These changes in spectra are in conformity with the betaine formulation of these compounds.

The two nitrogen atoms in the molecule of azacarbazoles have differing tendencies, i.e. the pyridine nitrogen is proton accepting and pyrrole nitrogen is proton donating. These opposing tendencies within the molecule should lead to large contribution of betaine type of structure (II) as shown. (of 7-azaindole)¹

1—and 2-azacarbazoles and their 6-nitro derivatives like 7-azaindole, readily quaternise with methyl iodide. The quaternary derivatives on treatment with alkali yield yellow basic substances which are readily extracted into chloroform. The products analysed well for the expected anhydro salts. These anhydro salts can be formulated as the normal covalent structure (III) and also as the betaine structure (IV).

Absorption spectra of these compounds in the visible and ultra-violet region was studied with a view to help in explaining the structures of certain naturally occurring alkaloids of which they go to constitute the main residue.

Freak and Robinson² synthesised α -N-methyl carboline in furtherance with the work on structure of harmine alkaloids and allied compounds. Schwarz and Schlittler³ studied the properties of β -N-methyl carboline to elucidate the structure of serpentine alkaloids. In the present work a study of the absorption spectra of these compounds in visible and ultra-violet region, in different solvents has been made. The spectra of the parent base for the sake of comparison has been taken from the literature⁴. A comparative study shows that the absorption spectra of these anhydro salts resemble that of the parent base except that, (1) there is a general bathochromic shift in the absorption maxima in the ultra-violet region, and (2) appearance of a new absorption maximum in the region of longer wavelength takes place which explains the colour of these anhydro salts (table I and II). The close agreement of extinction values of maxima in ultra-violet region indicates that they correspond to similar absorption processes. It may be seen that in the case of anhydro salts the excitation occurs with greater ease as indicated by the general bathochromic shift of the total spectrum. The influence of introduction of a nitro group in position 6-is seen in the bathochromic shift of the maxima in ultra-violet region. Like the phenol betaines^{5,6} the appearance of the characteristic band in the longer wavelengths should correspond to an alternative mode of excitation which is the betaine form of the molecule. The close correspondence of absorption maxima in ultra-violet region indicates that there is no fundamental change in the structural type (III) and that the betaine formulation satisfies the requirements for the absorption in the longer wavelengths.

TABLE I

Absorption spectra of anhydro salts derived from 1-azacarbazole and 2-azacarbazole (III a and b, R = H) in different solvents

Compound	λ max	λ max	λ max	λ max
1-azacarbazole I (a) in dioxane	—	347 m μ 3.66 238 m μ 2.76	288 m μ 4.12	225-30 m μ 4.56
III (a) in ethanol	398-400 m μ 3.41	318 m μ 4.09	278 m μ 4.4	220 m μ 4.41
III (a) in chloroform	412 m μ 3.25	315 m μ 4.15	272 m μ 4.35	—
2-azacarbazole I (b) in dioxane	—	342 m μ 3.79	285 m μ 4.4	220-30 m μ 4.7
III (b) in ethanol	435-40 m μ 3.42	308 m μ 4.15	283 m μ 4.43	262 m μ 4.42
III (b) in chloroform	450-60 m μ Inf. 2.1	313 m μ 4.25	284 m μ 3.70	266 m μ 4.37

2. R. Freak and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2013.
3. G. Schwarz and E. Schlittler; *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1951, 34, 629.
4. L. Horner, *Annalen*, 1939, 540, 77.
5. J. P. Saxena; *J. Sci. industr. Res.*; 1963, 22 b, 81-83.
6. J. P. Saxena, W. H. Stafford and W. L. Stafford, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1579.

TABLE II

Absorption spectra of anhydro salts derived from 6-nitro-1-azacarbazole and 6-nitro-2-azacarbazole (III a and b, R = NO₂) in different solvents

Compound	λ max	λ max	λ max	λ max
6-nitro-1-azacarbazole	—	330 m μ	302 m μ	228 m μ
I (a) in ethanol	—	3.8	4.06	4.06
III (a) in ethanol	380-85 m μ	365-70 m μ	308 m μ	229-30 m μ
	4.02	4.02	4.4	4.56
III (a) in chloroform	405-10 m μ	350-60 m μ	302 m μ	238 m μ
	Inf. 3.05	Inf. 3.81	4.35	4.17
6-nitro-2-azacarbazole	—	372 m μ	282-83 m μ	238 m μ
I (b) in ethanol	—	3.74	4.44	4.38
III (b) in ethanol	430-32 m μ	385 m μ	317 m μ	259 m μ
	3.8	3.9	4.39	4.39
III (b) in chloroform	448-50 m μ	380 m μ	317 m μ	259 m μ
	Inf. 2.2	3.65	4.27	4.17

Inf.=Inflection. Values in parentheses refer to log ϵ values.

In common with the phenol betaines⁶, the absorption spectra of these anhydro salts show considerable dependence on the solvent used. The influence of solvents takes place in two ways, (i) due to dipolar interaction with the polar solvent molecules and (ii) due to hydrogen bonding. It was observed that these compounds

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

were insoluble in hexane (nonpolar) in which as in the case of anhydro salts of 7-azaindole¹, the solvation energy of the polar anhydro salt being minimal, should have caused the appearance of maximum at a higher wavelength. As shown in figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 there is a blue shift in the characteristic absorption maximum in the longer wavelengths in ethanolic medium (hydroxylic solvent) as compared to that in chloroform (polar solvent). This effect is attributed to hydrogen bonding which is exhibiting greater influence as compared to dipolar interaction. This feature is analogous to the metho-, benzyl- and *p*-nitro benzyl betaines of 7-azaindole. The metho- and benzyl- betaines of 7-azaindole are soluble in hexane (nonpolar) in which they show the characteristic maximum absorption at a wavelength higher than that in ethanol or chloroform, their solvation energy in the polar state being much smaller, causes absorption at a higher wavelength. By analogy, *p*-nitro benzyl betaine of 7-azaindole and betaines of various azacarbazoles described above, which are insoluble in hexane, should have caused the appearance of absorption maximum at a higher wavelength in hexane. The shifts suffered by the characteristic absorption maxima of these compounds due to solvent interaction (shown above) is also identical and is found to be of a much lesser degree as compared to the phenol betaines⁶. This is possibly due to the comparative ease with which the $=\bar{N}$ betaines revert to the classical covalent forms III (a) and III (b). However the appearance of a characteristic absorption maximum in the longer wavelength and its dependence on solvent interaction is satisfied by the betaine formulation (dipolar form) of these compounds. The two canonical forms III and IV of these compounds account for their stability.

EXPERIMENTAL

Spectroscopically pure solvents were used for spectral work. 6-nitro derivatives of 1-aza- and 2-azacarbazole were prepared by the method described by Saxena⁷.

Methiodides of 1-azacarbazole, 2-azacarbazole and their 6-nitro derivatives :— These were prepared by dissolving the desired azacarbazole in Analar acetone and then boiling it under reflux with excess of methyl iodide on a water bath for half an hour. A solid separated which was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. Quantitative yields of the methiodides were obtained.

Methiodide of 1-azacarbazole :—It was obtained as white needles, m.p. 224°. Found C, 44.3 ; H, 3.7 ; N, 8.5 and I, 38.5. $C_{12}H_{11}N_2I/H_2O$ requires C, 43.9 ; H, 3.9 ; N, 8.3 and I, 38.8.

Methiodide of 2-azacarbazole :—It was obtained as white needles. m.p. 237°. Found C, 46.2 ; H, 4.0 ; N, 8.8 ; and I, 41.0. $C_{12}H_{11}N_2I$ requires C, 46.0 ; H, 3.54 ; N, 9.03 and I, 40.9.

Methiodide of 6-nitro-1-azacarbazole :—It gave yellow needles from methanol. m.p. 345° (with charring). Found C, 40.8 ; H, 2.78% ; N, 12.1 and I, 36.2. $C_{12}H_{10}N_3O_2I$ requires C, 40.6 ; H, 2.82 ; N, 11.8 ; and I, 35.8.

Methiodide of 6-nitro-2-azacarbazole :—It gave yellow needles from ethanol, m.p. 256-57°. Found C, 40.3 ; H, 2.75 ; N, 11.3 and I, 35.5. $C_{12}H_{10}N_3O_2I$ requires N_3O_2I C, 40.6 ; H, 2.82 ; N, 11.8 : and I, 35.82.

Anhydro salts from the methiodides of Azacarbazoles :—The following general procedure was adopted for the preparation of anhydro salts from the respective methiodides. The desired methiodide was dissolved in limited quantity of water and was basified with 2N potassium carbonate solution. A deep yellow colour of the betaine developed which was extracted into chloroform. The chloroform layer was dried on anhydrous sodium sulphate and then filtered. To the concentrated solution of betaine in chloroform dry benzene was added while it was hot. On cooling the crystals of betaine separated out. The yield of betaine was 78-80%.

1-methyl-1-azacarbazolium hydroxide anhydro salt crystallised as yellow rosettes, m.p. 131-132°. Found C, 78.7 ; H, 5.7 ; N, 15.2. $C_{12}H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 79.1 ; H, 5.5 ; N, 15.4.

2-methyl-2-azacarbazolium hydroxide anhydro salt crystallised as yellow needles, m.p. 197-98°. Found C, 79.0 ; H, 5.3 ; N, 15.0. $C_{12}H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 79.1 ; H, 5.5 ; N, 15.4.

6-nitro-1-methyl-1-azacarbazolium hydroxide anhydro salt crystallised as yellow needles, m.p. 289-90°. Found C, 63.1 ; H, 4.1 ; N, 18.5. $C_{12}H_9N_3O_2$ requires C, 63.4 ; H, 4.0 ; N, 18.5.

6-nitro-2-methyl-2-azacarbazolium hydroxide anhydro salt crystallised as yellow needles, m.p. 236-38°. Found C, 63.2 ; H, 4.2 ; N, 18.7. $C_{12}H_9N_3O_2$ requires C, 63.4 ; H, 4.0 ; N, 18.5.